

Systematic Security Context Weighting for Trust Algorithms via AI/ML Model Performance Analysis

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Abstract. Malicious actors can introduce poisoned data by exploiting security vulnerabilities that may be present anywhere in networked systems. Depending on how the data is processed and used, this can have severe and potentially catastrophic effects. Using the data produced in such systems for the generation and evaluation of Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML) models, one may identify if malicious data is being introduced, though not necessarily where the intrusions occur. In this work we exploit the availability of metadata that is associated with the security context in which data is collected, transported and processed, as would be available, for example, in a data confidence fabric. We use this metadata in combination with iterative data weighting informed by that context. This facilitates the isolation of potential attack vectors or vulnerabilities by systematically training and evaluating low-impact AI/ML models while adjusting individual context weighting to discover the outlier features. With this approach, we can identify specific security or safety contexts of high significance based on anomalous impacts on model accuracy and loss evaluation computations.

1 Introduction

Ensuring a high degree of data integrity has always been essential to the correct operation of computer systems. With the increasing use of machine learning, the role of data in determining a plethora of important decisions has become central to so many aspects of human activity, including, inter alia, industry, healthcare, transport, education and security. Security context in the form of metadata is increasingly important in inter-connected systems wherein equipment and software can come from a wide variety of sources, with differing installation and update histories, software revisions and behaviour patterns. Recent developments in the area of Data Confidence Fabrics (Section 2.2) enable reliable context annotation to be associated with devices and data in connected systems, which we exploit to match data impact on AI/ML models to the originating contexts that produced that data. By including data provenance and security context as a contributor to relatively low-complexity AI/ML models (via iterative context weighting) we

can evaluate which contexts are significant and may be potential vectors for malicious or erroneous material when those contexts differ or are absent.

The main contribution of this paper is the development and demonstration of an accuracy- and loss-based approach for anomaly isolation for applications incorporating heterogeneous data source security contexts, using AI/ML models with iterative data weightings based on these contexts to identify which security contexts may be significant. These models need not be complex, as they are not necessarily intended for direct use but instead need only be sophisticated enough to produce the anomalous accuracy or loss results. Where critical security contexts are identified, this information can be relayed to the rest of the network in the form of Trust weightings for use by Trust Algorithms – in Cloud-Edge systems this is particularly useful as the relatively high compute power closer to the cloud can generate the AI/ML testing models, while the relative importance of security contexts can be relayed to less-powerful equipment nearer the edge in the form of weight values for security annotations.

1.1 Threat Model

In this work, we assume a data processing application incorporating data from live data streams (e.g. sensor readings, camera feeds), one or more pre-existing datasets, or a combination of data sources having a variety of provenances. We assume a bad actor intends to interfere with the data processing and analysis through the insertion of “poisoned” data, either via the live streams or as part of input datasets. This poisoning can take on many forms, be it the alteration of numerical values, the falsification of data source identifiers, class label fraud [15], subtle or overt alterations to images or audio [9] [22] or using techniques to avoid automated identification of image features, e.g. altering machine generated images to mask their artificial origins.

The assumed intent of this attack is to induce poor performance or engineered outcomes in data processing, machine learning or AI model training. With this assumption in mind, successful data poisoning should result in material changes to such models trained on the poisoned material, and as such, we propose an approach using model loss functions (Section 3.1) as a method to identify the contexts which protect against the poisoned material entering the dataset, and which contexts – when absent – can lead to poor quality or malicious contributions to datasets.

1.2 Structure

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: We describe the benefits and use of security context for networked systems processing and exchanging data, followed by a description of our Trust Weighting approach for exploiting security context metadata as a means of identifying relative important of certain security or provenance contexts. We then describe some preliminary experiments for evaluating the potential efficacy of this approach and explore the results. We follow this up with more in-depth experiments with virtual devices for Image

Classification problems, exploring iterative weighting in pursuit of identifying significant contexts. Finally we describe related work and their relationship with our work, concluding with our findings and possible future work.

2 Contextual Metadata for Trust and Security

A number of technical solutions for maintaining and asserting data provenance have emerged in recent years, in data usage and processing contexts as diverse as sensor processing, social media, data sanitation, media and news trust and copyright and IP enforcement.

2.1 Zero Trust Environments

Applications and systems running in environments without implicit trust [20] require another means of determining whether (or how much) to allow the participation of users, devices or data sources in those applications and systems. To achieve this, Zero Trust (ZT) environments make use of contextual information and Trust Algorithms – schemes using verifiable security and reputation context as input for determining how much Trust those sources merit, and/or which applications they are permitted to contribute to or access information from. In data collection applications – especially those conducted across an extended period of time or incorporating a variety of contributors – the nature of the equipment used to collect data as well as the software revisions present on that equipment may exhibit large variation in capability, reliability and security features [5].

In the case of applications or models making use of a mix of historical data, contextual information about those datasets may include: methodologies, personnel qualifications, data collection apparatus, empirical quality analyses. [11]

Federated systems amalgamate data feeds from multiple participants through federation protocols such as ActivityPub [4] and Authenticated Transfer Protocol (ATproto) [12]. These systems permit the exchange of messages between participants through these protocols provided that the participants accept each other's participation. Through reputation and moderation, individual participants may be filtered by others - for instance, a server may be filtered out entirely by another based on its moderation history (such as tolerance of bad actors) or if it has been identified as having been compromised by nefarious actors. These servers can continue to operate as usual but their material is blocked from reaching users on servers that have determined not to federate with them. In the case of protocols using personal user moderation and user graphs, exchange of trust and reputation information between users (through labels or feeds) can improve the quality of those users' experiences.

2.2 Data Confidence Fabrics

Technologies such as Alvarium [2], C2PA [7] and the Content Authenticity Initiative's (CAI) "Content Credentials" [8] incorporate contextual metadata to

provide the history and security/trust contexts for data where it is generated, edited, processed and relayed throughout networks or systems. Distributed Confidence Fabrics like Alvarium maintain this metadata in a communal, distributed resource such as a hashgraph or blockchain ledger, or through access to message brokers and metadata storage databases. Metadata is not stored with the data nor does it traverse networks with it, but the metadata history for any given datum is retrievable through the use of data keys (derived from hashes of the data itself) Conversely, C2PA and similar technologies include the security context metadata with the data itself, including the context information (provenance, history, edit types, equipment, software revision etc) within the data payload itself. This alleviates the need for maintaining a communal/distributed resource for metadata management, but may reveal some sensitive organisational or operational information to third parties receiving the data files.

2.3 Asserting Context

Security context for data is asserted based on the associated metadata, which may be verifiable using Data Confidence Fabrics, Zero-knowledge proofs, checksums and data history logs. DCF annotations provide context regarding a variety of security technologies present at devices through which data has passed or been processed or altered. Among these technologies that can be verified include: Transport Layer Security (TLS), data checksums, Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), Trusted Platform Module (TPM)

Further context can be ascertained through software revision tracking tools such as Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) [6], and installation history/personnel logs that may be available at an organisational level. In this work we acknowledge that a variety of technologies and schemes are available for identifying particular security/trust contexts, but we are agnostic as to which schemes are in use – merely that some method is used to determine whether or not particular trust/security criteria are met/present. For our experiments we make use of the Alvarium DCF annotation schema which annotates whether TLS, PKI, Checksum, SBOM, TPM and Source Verification security checks have been passed or not at each device, but Alvarium and other DCFs allow for a variety of contexts to be captured.

3 Contextual Trust Weighting in AI and ML models

Machine learning and AI models typically support the ability to weight entries according to the needs of the model user. Weightings are often used as a means to avoid over-representation of certain classes of data in datasets, or to reflect relative quality differences. Weightings are implemented either through increasing the contribution of heavily weighted datapoints to training, or through “oversampling”: training the model with duplicates of the higher weighted datapoints according to the desired contribution. In this work, we adopt the data weighting scheme in order to selectively increase the contribution of certain datapoints

according to the security context as formulated based on the present or absent security features (as “annotations”).

In our earlier work [16], we demonstrated the utility of trust scoring as source of data weighting in ML training. In this work, we showed that accounting for trust allows for the use of mixed provenance data while maintaining a large training dataset for linear regression and random forest classification problems. In this work we look instead to isolating critical annotation types as potentially the most significant, which provides feedback for trust scoring algorithms (and hence, for data weight setting in future).

3.1 Loss Functions for Model Analysis

In this work we make use of loss functions as a tool for identifying outliers in trained models where certain security contexts are weighted differently than others. Loss functions are measuring tools for characterising how well a model’s trained perspective of a domain reflects that of the domain itself. Loss can be used as a way to evaluate accuracy of predictions – as with the co-efficient of determination (R^2) [27], or to compare the distance between the probability distributions of a trained model and the distributions in the data – as with Kullback–Leibler divergence (KL) [13]. Loss functions provide useful insights into the quality of AI/ML models beyond simple accuracy statistics, as for instance, an image classification model may typically identify the correct class for a high percentage of presented images, but may not be especially confident in the classifications themselves. An accuracy metric may score highly but a poor loss function result indicates the model is not robust or may have trained on faulty material. This method of evaluation is particularly useful for models using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) as it allows for a concise metric for evaluation of otherwise complex models, beyond simply measuring classification accuracy. By observing that some features are more significant than others, the dimensionality of classification models can be reduced and performance improved for intrusion detection into the data source.

3.2 Annotation Weighting

For each data entry d we compute the trust-weighting value for that data according to this formula:

$$d_{weighting} = \sum_{i=0}^{i=n-1} w_i * a_i(d) \quad (1)$$

where w_i is the global annotation weighting value for annotation i in this iteration of model training, and a_i is 1 or 0 depending on whether that annotation is or isn’t present and verified for this particular data entry d . Relative performance of models trained on data with these weightings provides the mechanism for isolating a possible critical security flaw or attack vectors – if there is a

significant security feature or technology, we expect model loss values to deviate positively from the mean when that feature is weighted highly vs alternative weightings.

3.3 Model Performance Analysis for Intrusion Detection

Using a clean test set we evaluate model performance based on prediction accuracy when trained with a set of mixed clean and poisoned material (but where the annotation weightings are taken into account).

Data for the training set is allocated evenly between 10 virtual devices, each having a different mix of present and absent security features. When data is retrieved from these devices it is annotated with the context annotations accurate for that device and collected centrally by the equipment conducting the iterative testing and model training. Where a device is missing the security feature on which the attack may be introduced, there is a chance that a piece of data it is supplying is modified or substituted in a manner that interferes with accuracy and/or loss values in models.

We conducted our experiments using iterative weighting of one of each annotation type per iteration, though where there is a suspicion of a particular security element (or lack thereof) being of importance, the weighting for this particular metadata element can be examined specifically in comparison to the baseline results. The experiments are repeated with increasing percentage chance of poisoning being introduced where the attack can exploit the targeted missing security feature.

Model Choice In our approach, the models used to isolate potential attack vectors need not be the same – or even similar – to the models used in practice in the systems or applications using the data ordinarily. As the task is to identify an anomalous source of data where certain context is asserted, we need only use models of sufficient capacity to reflect the probability distributions of input data such that the likely poisoning approaches would result in perceptible changes in loss function results. In practice, the choice of models used can be relatively lightweight, using parameters that don't result in computation effort similar to usual data applications – however, the choice of model should align with the application goals such that a nefarious actor attempting to interfere with the application would result in perceptible outliers in both the lightweight test models and the intensive application models. As such, where images are used for classification problems in our application, we should also use image classification models as the basis for our intrusion detection battery – but we can use lightweight models, with fewer training iterations/epochs as our ultimate goal in this activity isn't training excellent models, but to identify relative differences in model performance as weightings change.

3.4 Systematic Training and Evaluation

We iteratively change the test vector and evaluate on accuracy and loss (Figure 1). For each entry in the input dataset, a set of flags are set according to whether or not a given piece of security context is present (termed “annotations” or “annos” after the Alvarium nomenclature). The data is split into 80/20% train and test sets, with the testing set representing a pristine data source (or in practical applications, the 20% of data with the greatest number of present and correct annotations – the data of best verifiable provenance available). We then train a number of models equal to one plus the total number of annotation flags (we test the elevated weighting for each individual annotation as well as none, for comparison). Each model has a different annotation selected as the testing vector - its weighting multiplier is set to an elevated value relative to the other annotations.

Loss is evaluated based on the trained model in comparison to the probability distributions of the test set. After identifying the loss function values for each target vector, their deviation from the mean of all the models in that round of evaluations are established with the target vector with the highest value identifying the security vector of erroneous or malicious data – this outlier has an increased contribution from data points where that particular security context is present versus absent.

Fig. 1: Systematic data weighting and model evaluation

Note: as each iteration/evaluation does not depend on the results of any others, this is an easily parallelized activity. In addition, as the models need not be especially complex, they can be computed on a variety of equipment

throughout a network (though, of course, the security context of the equipment performing this distributed work is also an important consideration).

4 Preliminary Experiments

In our earlier work [16] we identified the utility of security context annotations as an input in ML problems, allowing for the use of trust values as a source for data weighting, balancing dataset size with trust considerations. In this work we used two datasets (a housing census dataset and a banking telemarketing dataset) and two ML modelling approaches (linear regression and decision tree) to explore the viability of that approach. In this section, we conduct preliminary experiments using the same data and model types with the use of selective annotation weighting to identify if a particular attack or poison vector can be isolated. In these experiments (housing and banking), we set aside a 20% subset of the dataset for testing purposes before applying any poisoning to the remaining training material.

4.1 Randomised Annotations and Data Poisoning

In each battery of experiments, we use 6 security feature annotations ("source", "pki", "tls", "tpm", "sbom" and "checksum") and select a single one ("tpm") as the potential vector for poisoned data, which represents the impact of a security weakness when this feature is absent. Depending on the round of modelling and evaluation, each of the 6 annotations have a percentage chance of being absent based on that round (10, 20, 30% etc). After setting the annotation flags, each data entry where the poisoning vector annotation is absent has a 25% chance for data poisoning (i.e. its data fields are altered in a manner which may degrade model performance/increase loss, specific to the model type as detailed in Section 4.1). In these experiments, the poison vector is the Trusted Platform Module – if this annotation is missing, there is a chance for the poisoned data to be introduced Following annotation setting and introducing poisoned data, the data weightings are applied, per Section 3.2, with a target weighting of 8. While the "attack" step where poisoned data is introduced is aware of "TPM" being absent as being the source of vulnerability, the iterative training and analysis steps are not. By testing each annotation vector equally, we should be able to observe which, if any, are the poisoned vector without prior information – if the experiments are successful we should be able to isolate TPM while giving all annotation types equal opportunity for selective weighting and testing (similarly if any other vector is the source of poison instead, that annotation should stand out).

Linear Regression The California Housing dataset [18] consists of housing census data from California, USA. This dataset was collected in 1990, and housing is measured on per-block basis with average number of bedrooms, median income, longitude and latitude and house valuation. We use this data to train

linear regression models (Random Forest with scikit) [26] for predicting the house valuation based on the other fields. These models are evaluated based on the coefficient of determination (R^2) as the loss function.

Decision Tree The Banking dataset consists of outcomes from a banking tele-marketing campaign conducted by a bank in Portugal [14], capturing savings amounts, education levels, job categories. This dataset was collected for the purposes of associating these fields with a Yes/No value for whether the customer being contacted accepted an offer of a particular banking product. In this work we use the bank balance, education class to train a Decision Tree model (scikit) [17] that predicts values for the customer’s Job (student, retiree, professional etc.) from one of 6 possible values. These models are evaluated based on the coefficient of determination (R^2) value.

Data Poisoning For each class of problem, we adopt a data poisoning approach which modifies the inputs for the models in a manner which is expected to cause a change to how the model performs. Each problem has certain fields which contribute strongly to the accuracy and precision of models trained on their respective data, and in order to induce a change in performance of the model, an attacker would target these fields.

We identify the targets for poisoning as follows:

Banking data: We swap the classification label of an entry’s job description to another value, reducing the capacity of models trained on the data to accurately predict this value in the training set.

Housing data: we adjust the latitude value of the entry northwards, which in practice results in housing which would otherwise be located in high-value urban/suburban areas to be treated as though it were in rural or inter-city areas of lower relative value.

4.2 Results

Linear Regression (California Housing) In our Housing data experiments (Figure 2), we observe that as the number of present annotations decreases, the proportion of poisoned data increases. When each annotation is selectively weighted, we are able to isolate the target vector “tpm” by noting its deviation from the mean of all the annotation weightings. As a greater proportion of the dataset is missing this attack vector security context in further iterations, the difference from the mean increases accordingly. As this is a linear regression model, the poisoning induces an increasing amount of error (observed via the loss function R^2).

Fig. 2: Housing Random Forest Regression results

Decision Tree Classification (Portuguese Banking) In our Banking experiments (Figure 3), we similarly observe the attack vector “tpm” can be isolated from the others by its deviation from the mean loss value. As we weight contributions where this annotation is present more highly, these models outperform the other weighting choices. As this is a classification problem, as the poisoning increases, the performance degrades to approach that of a random guess of the possible values, which is observable in the “tpm” result at increasing poisoning percentages, though it still out-performs alternative weightings.

5 CNN Image Classification Experiments

To expand on our preliminary experiments and to explore the impact of poisoning and the potential benefits of context weighting, a further battery of experiments were conducted using Convolutional Neural Networks for image classification. Unlike in the preliminary experiments for housing and banking data, in these experiments a collection of 10 virtual devices are pre-configured with different security contexts present from the 6 available annotation types (Table 1). Each device is allocated an equal share of the training data which they report to a central virtual device along with their security contexts (i.e. annotation true/false

Fig. 3: Banking Decision Tree results

values) which converts these into data entry weightings and conducts model training accordingly. The target annotation weighting is initially set to 2, while all other annotation flags have a weighting multiplier of 1. In further iterations of the experiment, the testing vector weighting is increased to 4, and then 8 to explore the role weighting has on identification of attack vectors and how the weighting value itself can reflect the degree of poisoning occurring and relative importance of annotations.

The dataset used for these experiments consists of a mix of fresh and rotten fruits and vegetable images [24]. We use six fresh fruits/vegetables (apples, bananas, jujubes, bell peppers, potatoes and strawberries, Figure 4) to train the model to classify the type of produce present, producing a CNN that classifies fruit type based on input images. These models are evaluated using Kullback–Leibler divergence (KL) as a loss function which is also the loss function used in the final evaluation in our results (Section 5.2).

A sequential model (Keras/tensorflow, based in part on an approach by Osama Abo-Bakr Khalifa [1]) is created to train on the input images, with the weighting scores provided as input at the input layer. The model is struc-

	Source	PKI	TLS	TPM	SBOM	Checksum
device0	True	True	True	True	True	True
device1	False	True	False	True	False	False
device2	True	True	True	True	True	False
device3	False	False	True	True	False	True
device4	False	True	True	False	True	True
device5	True	False	False	False	True	True
device6	True	False	True	True	True	False
device7	False	False	False	True	False	True
device8	False	True	True	True	False	True
device9	False	True	True	False	True	False

Table 1: Virtual Device Security Configuration

Fig. 4: Fruit/Veg dataset

tured as follows:

Image Classification CNN architecture

```
Conv2D(filters=9, kernel\_size=(5, 5), input\_shape=(128, 128, 3))
Activation('relu')
MaxPooling2D((3, 3))
Conv2D(filters=64, kernel\_size=(5, 5) )
Activation('relu')
MaxPooling2D((2, 2))
Conv2D(filters=128, kernel\_size=(4, 4))
Activation('relu')
MaxPooling2D((2, 2))
Conv2D(filters=128, kernel\_size=(3, 3))
Activation('relu')
MaxPooling2D((2, 2))
Flatten()
Dense(512, activation='relu')
Dropout(0.5)
Dense(64, activation='relu')
Dense(6, activation='softmax')
```

5.1 Image data poisoning

Where a given virtual device in possession of a subset of the overall training set is missing the security feature through which poisoned material might be introduced (the poisoning vector), some of the data entries it reports to the central node have a chance to be substituted with an image pulled from a set of rotten oranges (Figure 5) found in the same dataset as the fresh fruit examples [24]. This results in some entries entering the training set having our standard fruit labels (strawberry, apple etc.) but having features not ordinarily present for those fruit classes (orange colour, grey splotches, different shape). As we increase the percentage chance for poisoning to occur, those virtual devices with the missing security feature contribute more and more poisoned material to the model training.

5.2 Image Classification Results

In our Fruit classification experiments (Figures 6 7, 8) we observe outcomes similar to the banking and housing classification tasks. With the target weightings of 2, 4, and 8 we find that the target vector (TPM) begins to separate from the other annotations when it is the candidate for special weighting, with the separation increasing as the poisoning increases (and at a rate consistent with the relative 2/4/8 weightings in the three sets of experiments). An interesting effect can be observed in that the "Source" annotation remains the nearest to the TPM results in all three weightings, though it doesn't consistently increase

Fig. 5: Examples of some Rotten Oranges used for data Poisoning

separation from the others in the manner that the TPM results do. This outcome would seem to be an effect of virtual devices with missing TPM annotations had a tendency to be missing their Source context as well. In the 2x weighting results, particularly for low or medium poisoning levels this might make the origin of poisoning difficult to identify, but with greater weightings and/or poisoning levels we can more clearly identify the significance of the TPM annotation. In this work we can observe a relationship between the proportion of input data that is being poisoned with the relative weighting of target annotations – where weightings are too low or the poisoning proportion is low, it can be difficult to isolate any particular vector. In future work we will explore selecting values and variables of statistical significance based on controllable parameters and iterative model training.

6 Related Work

Model evaluations using loss functions have been conducted in data poisoning and model protection research, including Hong et al [10]. In their work, they analyse differences between trained gradients in ML models (e.g. back propagation values in a Neural Network) which have been variously trained using clean and poisoned data. They employ a gradient shaping mechanism to lower the impact of possibly poisoned data on models during training, based on how much magnitude of a change in loss function they would cause. In our work, we similarly evaluate the impact on model loss function as a means to identify possibly poisoned material, but using security context metadata to associate such material with the possible vulnerability allowing such material to be introduced. Practices for intrusion detection with feature selection have been explored by Sommer and Paxson [23]. In their work, they categorise machine learning approaches for analysing network behaviour for intrusion detection, noting that these algorithms are generally designed to identify *similarities* between events rather than iden-

Fig. 6: CNN Fruit Classification results – Target Weight 2x

tifying outliers and anomalies. In our work we identify the anomalies based on loss functions of the models themselves, capturing the difference in probability distribution based on iterative weighting. In our work we leverage technologies that provide trust context metadata for establishing data provenance. Examples are the Linux Foundation’s Alvarium system [2], C2PA [21], Exif and IPTC media metadata [19] [25]. Software and hardware sources of security context are available through technologies such as the Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) [28] or Trusted Platform Modules (TPM) [3].

7 Conclusions and Future Work

In our work we demonstrated an effective technique for identifying and isolating a potential source of data interference in datasets and data sources through iteratively emphasising each single element of security/provenance metadata and observing the impact on AI/ML model loss function results. In future work we will explore systematic techniques for isolated multiple possible attack vectors, such as through branch-and-bound-like search schemes weighing several annotation/metadata features simultaneously to both speed up the search task where many annotations are to be considered, and to allow for multiple potential intru-

Fig. 7: CNN Fruit Classification results – Target Weight 4x

sion sources to be identified without generating and testing a very large number of models. Where several security features are absent, there may be compromised material arriving from otherwise disjoint security states simultaneously, which may present interesting challenges and opportunities for our approach. We made use of the security contexts that are available through the Alvarium Data Confidence Fabric, but other contexts exist whether as part of other frameworks or as custom evaluation in Zero Trust environments. In future work we will explore having large numbers of “annotations” be they from frameworks or custom analyses (such as installation history or a reputation score).

In our Image Classification experiments, we progressively increased the weighting of the contributions from data with the significant security context, providing some insight into relative importance of that context in the given application/system. In future work we will explore applications for sharing these weighting values with other parts of a networked system where Trust Algorithms may be in use, allowing for the relative security significance of these contexts to be incorporated in other kinds of data or device use decisions. Our work made use of virtual devices and a simplified data collection scheme. In future work we will explore real-world deployments with a variety of equipment types and security configurations, as well as more realistic data collection contexts (col-

Fig. 8: CNN Fruit Classification results – Target Weight 8x

lection over time from real sensors etc). We presented an early-stage framework for the identification and isolation of significant security contexts, in future we will explore formalising and automating this approach so that automated systems can determine through quantitative/statistical means whether intrusions are occurring without immediate human observation.

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